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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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THE ROLE OF A RUBRIC IN ASSESSING THE ENGLISH SKILLS OF LEARNERS WITH VISUAL IMPAIRMENTS

Sharipova Yoqut Qudratillayevna
UzSWLU, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Abstract: For learners with visual impairments, the assessment of English has lagged behind the adaptation of materials and teaching. This article describes an ability-focused rubric grounded in Vygotsky's compensation principle and Universal Design for Learning. It scores four competencies - vocabulary and touch-based meaning, grammar, intelligible pronunciation, and Braille literacy with assistive technology - from 1 to 5, and lets a pupil answer in Braille, by voice, or through a screen reader. Trialled with 128 pupils in grades 5-6 across three Uzbek boarding schools, it gave the adapted-materials group a 13.3% advantage over a matched control (Pearson's chi-square = 9.39, $p < .05$) - a fair, reliable, and motivating basis for inclusive assessment.

Key words: inclusive assessment, rubric, Braille literacy, English as a foreign language, Universal Design for Learning, visual impairment.

Аннотация: Ko'rish qobiliyati cheklangan o'quvchilar uchun ta'lim materiallari takomillashib bormoqda, biroq ularning ingliz tili bilimini baholash usullari ortda qolmoqda. Maqolada qobiliyatga yo'naltirilgan, Vygotskiyning kompensatsiya tamoyili va Universal Dizayn (UDL) g'oyalari tayangan baholash rubrikasi tavsiflanadi. Rubrika to'rt kompetensiyani - leksik-taktil idrok, grammatika, talaffuz hamda Brayl savodxonligi va yordamchi texnologiyalardan foydalanishni - 1 dan 5 gacha baholaydi va o'quvchiga Brayl, nutq yoki ekran o'qigichi orqali javob berish imkonini beradi. Toshkent, Samarqand va Qashqadaryo viloyatlaridagi uchta maktab-internatda 5-6-sinflarda 128 o'quvchi ishtirokida o'tkazilgan tajriba-sinov natijalariga ko'ra, tajriba guruhida nazorat guruhiga nisbatan 13,3% yuqori natija qayd etildi (Pirsonning xi-kvadrat mezoni 9,39; $p < 0,05$). Rubrika bunday o'quvchilarni adolatli va rag'batlantiruvchi tarzda baholashga xizmat qiladi.

Калит so'zlar: inklyuziv baholash, rubrika, Brayl savodxonligi, ingliz tili, Universal Dizayn (UDL), ko'rish qobiliyati cheklanganlik.

Аннотация: Учебные материалы для учащихся с нарушениями зрения совершенствуются, однако способы оценивания их знаний по английскому языку отстают. В статье предлагается ориентированная на способности рубрика, опирающаяся на принцип компенсации Л.С. Выготского и идеи универсального дизайна обучения (UDL). Она оценивает четыре компетенции - лексико-тактильную, грамматическую, фонетическую и владение Брайлем с использованием вспомогательных технологий - по шкале от 1 до 5 и позволяет отвечать шрифтом Брайля, устно или с помощью программы экранного доступа. Аprobация с участием 128 учащихся 5-6 классов в трёх школах-интернатах (Ташкент, Самарканд, Кашкадарья) показала преимущество экспериментальной группы над контрольной в 13,3% (критерий хи-квадрат Пирсона 9,39; $p < 0,05$). Рубрика обеспечивает более справедливое и мотивирующее оценивание этих учащихся.

Ключевые слова: инклюзивное оценивание, аналитическая рубрика, грамотность по Брайлю, английский язык, универсальный дизайн обучения (UDL), нарушение зрения.

INTRODUCTION

A foreign language now counts as part of a complete schooling and as a route into higher study and work, and inclusive-education policy treats access to it as an entitlement rather than a favour^[1]. For pupils who cannot see, that entitlement narrows along the whole path from syllabus to teaching to testing, and testing is almost always the last part to be adapted^[2]. The research record reflects the same order of priorities: studies of English for these learners have concentrated on materials and classroom technique, while assessment has gone largely unexamined^[3].

Two problems explain why assessment resists adaptation. One is mechanical: a paper written for sighted pupils and reissued with extra time or a Braille copy still rests on the printed page, so it measures how easily

a child reaches the print as much as the English underneath, whereas Universal Design for Learning builds access into the task itself^[4]. The other is the habit of recording what a child cannot do, when the evidence runs the other way: with suitable input and tools, these learners often develop sharp auditory memory and oral skill^[3], a pattern Vygotsky's principle of compensation explains, as the loss of one sense pushes hearing, touch and inner speech to take over^[5]. In Uzbekistan, this is a matter of current policy - the 2020-2025 Concept for inclusive education (Presidential Decree No. 4860) has broadened provision for disabled learners^[6] - yet validated tools for assessing their English remain rare^[7]. Working inside the "Light Up" project of Braille-based, multisensory English materials for grades 5 and 6, this study builds an ability-focused, diagnostic-compensatory rubric and tests it in a controlled experiment, guided by three questions:

1. How does the rubric measure the English skills of visually impaired students?
2. What is the rubric's foundation, and how does it emphasize student strengths over weaknesses?
3. Did the experiment show measurable, statistically significant English improvements when using this rubric?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Vygotsky's defectology supplies the starting point: a missing sense does not subtract from development but reorganises it, as other channels take on the eye's work^[5]. In language learning, this yields a familiar profile - relative ease in listening and speaking, with reading and writing carried by Braille^[3] - and reviews find that, suitably taught and resourced, these learners are not disadvantaged and may even gain in verbal and auditory processing. Practice trails behind: teachers report scarce materials, thin training, and doubt about fair assessment^[3], and in systems such as Uzbekistan, materials tend to be transcribed into Braille rather than designed for access^[7].

A rubric names what a task is judged on and describes each level of quality; the analytic kind scores criteria one by one, giving finer diagnostic detail and, built with care, more consistent scores than a single mark^[8]. Its dependability rests on criteria tied to the learning aims, observable descriptors, and a manageable number of levels^[8] - none of which a print-based rubric can meet for a child who reads by touch. Four ideas shape the instrument reported here: Vygotsky's compensation and Krashen's affective-filter hypothesis place it on an ability footing and explain its delivery through games rather than a tense examination^[9]; Universal Design for Learning supplies the open, multi-channel response format^[2; 4]; Nation's depth-of-processing account shapes vocabulary tasks that reward understanding over recall^[10]; Celce-Murcia's communicative intelligibility weights pronunciation on stress and intonation rather than accent^[11]; and Black and William's case for feedback over marks gives every band a forward-looking descriptor^[12]. What the field still lacks is a validated, ability-focused rubric for assessing these learners' English, especially at primary level and in settings such as Uzbekistan - the gap this study addresses.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The five-point grading system traditionally used in Uzbek schools was adapted for learners with visual impairments. Rather than simply computing a percentage of correct answers, it also measures communicative initiative, Braille literacy, and auditory-tactile awareness. The framework rests on four core criteria, each scored from 1 to 5 with explicit band descriptors and assessed through signature tasks that engage hearing and touch rather than sight (Table 1).

Table 1: The ability-focused rubric: four criteria, each scored from 1 to 5

Criterion	5 Excellent	4 Good	3 Satisfactory	2 Weak	1 Poor
Vocabulary and tactile-semantic perception	Identifies object by touch at once; names and describes it unprompted	Names it correctly; needs a prompt to describe or use it	Hesitates; gives L1 first; vocabulary stays passive	Cannot identify by touch; repeats words mechanically	Declines; no vocabulary formed
Grammatical construction	Builds sentences accurately; self-corrects unaided	Correct word order; minor errors fixed when noticed	Relies on L1 logic; rules known but not applied	No grasp of structure; isolated words only	No grammatical awareness
Intelligible pronunciation	Fluent and clear; accurate stress and intonation	Clear; errors on hard sounds; intonation sometimes flat	Frequent errors that change meaning; halting speech	Heavy errors; speech hard to follow	Declines to speak

Braille literacy and technology	Fast, accurate Braille; independent with QR codes and readers	Independent but slow; rare dot errors, self-corrected	Slow, many errors; needs help with audio	Struggles to read dots; cannot use technology	Braille not formed
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The instrument was trialled in specialised boarding schools for visually impaired children in Tashkent city and the Samarkand and Qashqadaryo regions. Through purposive sampling, 128 pupils in grades 5 and 6 took part: 71 in an experimental group taught with the adapted “Light Up 5” and “Light Up 6” materials, and 57 in a control group following the usual ones. Class sizes differ because groups form naturally, so the two were matched on grade, conditions, and starting level, with consent from schools, guardians, and pupils. The experiment ran in four phases across 2024-2025 - diagnosis, preparation, teaching, and analysis - both groups taught by the researcher over identical hours and topics, and all 128 pupils sat a pre-test and a post-test scored on the rubric. Levels were coded high = 3, medium = 2, low = 1; group means and an efficiency coefficient (their ratio) were computed, and the difference between groups was tested with Student’s t-test, Pearson’s chi-square test, and the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The work produced the four-criterion instrument shown in Table 1, which answers the second question directly: in place of a record of deficits, it credits the speed of auditory memory and tactile perception, rewards self-correction, and treats independent use of Braille and technology as the mark of autonomy. At the outset, the two groups were level - means of 1.82 and 1.78 - and neither Pearson’s chi-square (0.22) nor the Kolmogorov-Smirnov statistic (0.11) approached its critical value, so they began as equals. After the programme, they parted company, as Figures 1 and 2 show.

Figure 1: Mean score, before and after

Figure 2: Performance levels after the programme

Figure 1 tracks the mean score: the groups begin together, then the experimental mean climbs to 2.04 while the control mean barely moves to 1.80, so almost all of the gain sits on the experimental side. Figure 2 shows the spread of attainment once the programme ended - the experimental low band (red) shrank from 40% to 19%, against little change in the control group.

The shift held up statistically. Pearson’s chi-square rose to 9.39 against a critical value of 5.99 at two degrees of freedom, and the Kolmogorov–Smirnov statistic reached 1.41 against 1.36, so both rejected the hypothesis of no difference in favour of the experimental group; expressed as a ratio of means, its attainment was 1.133 times the control’s - 13.3% higher.

The rubric did its job. Used as the measuring instrument in a controlled trial, it separated two groups that had started equal - a clear gain where adapted materials were used and near-stillness where they were not - behaviour that matches the rubric literature [8] and is here carried into a population and a set of channels (auditory, tactile, and Braille) it has rarely reached. The instrument also carries its theory: by scoring what a learner can do through whatever channel suits, it keeps language ability clear of print access [4], credits the auditory and tactile strengths compensation predicts [5], lowers anxiety by being delivered as play [9], and, through its described bands, makes assessment formative [12].

For a country reforming inclusive education, such as Uzbekistan, the rubric offers a concrete tool to set beside policy and to guide teacher training [6; 7]. The findings are nonetheless preliminary: sampling was purposive, the groups were unequal because classes form naturally, and the trial reached only grades 5 and 6 in three regions. The study reports on the rubric in use rather than testing inter-rater consistency; that check, ideally after rater training, is the first priority for further work, alongside larger samples.

CONCLUSION

Inclusion is most easily lost at the moment of assessment, when a pupil taught through accessible materials is judged by an inaccessible test. The rubric set out here assesses the English of visually impaired learners by what they can do - in Braille, in speech, through technology - on a five-point scale whose bands are plainly described. In a controlled trial with 128 pupils, it recorded a 13.3% advantage for adapted teaching, confirmed by two statistical tests; with wider validation, it gives teachers in Uzbekistan and comparable settings a fair, workable instrument and a model of assessment built to include from the start.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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Mas'ul muharrir: Ramzidin Ashurov

Ingliz tili muharriri: Murod Xoliyorov

Musahhih: Alibek Zokirov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

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